

Informed Consent Form for Research Data Collection and Usage

1. Purpose of Data Collection & Research Data collected during Kichikae sessions is used to ensure effectiveness and safety, and specifically for:

- Verification of the effects of Kichikae exercises.
- Development of enhanced exercise programs.
- **Academic contributions to the field of movement and rehabilitation science.**

2. Types of Data Used for Research The following data may be processed for research purposes:

- Health-related data: blood pressure, heart rate, and physical condition survey responses.
- Session progress records. (Note: All personal identifiers are removed for quantitative analysis.)

3. Confidentiality and Anonymization

- Research data will be **anonymized** and stored strictly for academic purposes.
- Personal identifiers (names, contact info) are **not** used in quantitative research analysis.
- Data is accessible only to qualified researchers under strict confidentiality.

4. Voluntary Participation & Withdrawal

- Participation in the research aspect is **voluntary**.
- Participants have the right to withdraw consent for research-related data usage at any time.
- Participants may refuse measurements at any time without affecting their service.

5. Participant Consent By signing the service agreement, the participant acknowledges that they have read and understood the above terms regarding the use of their anonymized data for scientific research purposes.

Signature: _____

Name: _____

Date: _____